

GSJ: Volume 7, Issue 11, November 2019, Online: ISSN 2320-9186
www.globalscientificjournal.com

Parents Perception of Children Physical Activity

Authors:

1. Kainat Jalal (Student of BSN) Jalalkainat@gmail.com +92 304-9434248
2. Iram Majeed (Faculty of Lahore School of Nursing Department, The University of Lahore) MS in Medical Imaging Technology (MS MIT), MSN, BSN.
3. Muhammad Afzal (HOD of Lahore School of Nursing Department, The University of Lahore) MSN, BSN, MBA (Health Management), MSC Hematology, BSC Microbiology.
4. Syed Amir Gilani (Dean of University of Lahore) MBBS, PhD in Medical Diagnostic Ultrasound, Master of Public Health, Diploma in Medical Radiology Diagnostics (DMRD) field of study Radiology, PhD Public Health.

Corresponding author: Kainat Jalal*

Mailing address: The University of Lahore, Pakistan1 - KM Defence Road, Lahore,
Pakistan. +92 (0)42 111-865-865

Fax: +924235321761

Mobile phone: +92 304-9434248

E-mail: jalalkainat@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: It was a belief of ancient philosophers and physicians like Plato and Hippocrates that there is a relationship between physical activity, health and disease. Physical activity plays a vital role for promotion of health and prevention of life style related disease in an individual. Physical activity promote development and growth in children, it enhances the motor skills, increase muscle and bone strength, loses fat. Children need weight control exercises for normal skeletal development. **Aim of study:** The main purpose of this study is to evaluate the parent's perception about their children physical activity. **Methodology:** Cross sectional study, survey type research model and quantitative data which is obtained through a reliable and valid scales are used in the study. The population for this study is the parents of primary school children in community of Ali Raza Abad. The study duration is 4 months. The questionnaire is adopted from Carman Ka-man Leung. The demographic data consist of 8 questions and the other section which is likert Scale questionnaire is consist of 70 questions. **Result:** The mean score for children physical competence is 2.31 and the overall mean score is ± 1.0505 . The mean score for parents support their children in physical activity is 0.88 and the overall mean score is ± 0.428 . The mean score for parents perception about neighborhood safety for children is 2.16 and the overall mean score is ± 0.84 . The mean score for the parents ideas about exercise is 1.99 and the overall mean score is ± 0.799 . **Conclusion:** This study examined parent's perceptions about children's competence of physical activity, neighborhood safety, exercise benefits and exercise barriers, parental support, and parents views about the children's physical activity. Each of the relationships among the above constructs was analyzed. Parent's involvement is very significant for children physical activity.

Keywords: Parents perception, Children, Physical Activity.

Introduction

Health is defined as the ability of a body to adapt threats and disabilities. Health also refers to complete emotional and physical well-being. Good health is essential to handle stress and to live an active life (Nordqvist, 2014). It was a belief of ancient philosophers and physicians like Plato and Hippocrates that there is a relationship between physical activity, health and disease (McKinney et al., 2016). Physical activity plays a vital role for promotion of health and prevention of life style related disease in an individual. Physical activity promote development and growth in children, it enhances the motor skills, increase muscle and bone strength, loses fat. Children need weight control exercises for normal skeletal development (Leung, 2014).

The benefits of physical activity is high bone mineral density and low symptoms of stress and depression. For children, physical activity encourages the good academic performance. Parents have a very significant role for shaping their children life-style, but the lack of knowledge and skills make it more difficult. The fundamental movement skills (FMS) in children consist of movement (e.g. jumping and running), object control (e.g. throwing and catching) and stability (e.g. balancing and twisting). The physical activity practices make children healthy and active throughout their lifespan (Ha, Ng, Lonsdale, Lubans, & Ng, 2019).

Children who were engage in the physical activity has a lower risk of cardiac and obesity related diseases. USA and UK indicates that the children who do not engage in the physical activities are less active as they became older. Usually parents are blamed for the inactivity of their children (Jago et al., 2017). Parents typically identify the significance of physical activity and restrictive screen time, but frequently model inactive lifestyles containing extreme TV watching and computer use. The impact of parental showing is usually evaluated by investigating relation between the same parent and child health behaviors (Schoeppe et al., 2016).

About 3.2 billion death occurred worldwide because of the physical inactivity and it is the fourth leading risk factor of death. 7-13 year old obese children have a greater chances of heart disease as they became adult. It was also estimated that an overweight and inactive parents are less likely to encourage their children for physical activity (Ahmed et al., 2016).

Physical activity competence supports children to stand efficiently and confidently in every physical related tough situation in their life. Physical activity make a children an efficient adult in future (Washburn & Kolen, 2018).

The youth whose parents did not participate in physical activity with their children have a very low interdependent activities related to those whose at least one parent participate. It helps parent's realize that their participation can impact on their child's future (Jennifer, 2017).

Neighborhood safety is very essential for the development of young children. The linkage between children development and neighborhood safety is understood by the present climate, the labors and the housing market promote concern about the crime and worsening in neighborhood (Datar, 2013).

The causes of obesity in children and adolescents have relation between inadequate dietary habits, sedentary life style and low physical activity (Lago-Ballesteros, 2019).

Outdoor play is very important for children, they become exposed to sunlight, open air, natural elements which can benefit for their bones development, stronger immune system and physical activity (Bento, 2017).

The impacts of physical inactivity are the fourth important reason of death globally. From initial childhood ahead, physical activity have a tendency to deterioration with age, and a large drop arises in late adolescence. Alterations occur among the genders for example, physical activity between girls frequently decrease during adolescence, as community impact and perceived social standards become issues affecting contribution in physical activity (Mikaelsson, 2019).

There are environmental and cultural barriers for ethnic groups related to physical activity which included, safety concern, adverse weather and lack of resources and in Muslim faith, who stated lack of culturally suitable physical activity for girls (Trigwell, 2015).

In USA per week about 21% of the adolescents meets 150 minutes physical activity. Physical activity rate is decreases in rural people than urban and suburban population because rural people did not meet the recommendation of physical activity. Because of decrease physical activity rural people are more at risk to have chronic diseases (Beck, 2019).

In Pakistan, mostly government schools have single-gender physical activity, which is not the situation in private schools. Leading actions contain sports and athletics. On physical activity time, students wear kit for doing physical activity. They join lessons in the same suit. They indorse gender-based physical activity starting from class one after clearing pre-participation

head-to-toe bodily examination. End-of-the-term appraisal should participate unclothed-physical examination with health testing. Examination should assess health as well as skill-related fitness (Kamal, 2014).

Problem Statement

Internationally, the decline in physical activity between children was assessed (Tremblay, 2014). The WHO report estimated inadequate physical activity in 122 countries, later the updated study estimated inadequate physical activity in 146 countries, the level of physical activity decreases (Guthold, 2018). In Pakistan, just 20% of children start one hour of physical activity four times a week, insufficient but consistent with data from WHO. Pakistan's research determine that about 30% of school-children were low, about 70% were moderate, and none had high physical activity levels. Higher level of physical activity are positively related to male gender, education in public school, parental support, and those who did schoolwork and played indoors (Jabeen, 2018). Study conduct to evaluate parents understanding of physical activity and competency of their children's physical activity, neighborhood safety, community health, parent involvement and encouragement, physical exercise benefits and barriers.

Research Question

What is the parent's perception of their children physical activity?

Significance of Study

Physical activity prevent many diseases and promote health. The behaviors associated with childhood physical activity leads to a balanced adulthood. Physical inactivity causes obesity that is responsible for many chronic diseases such as cardiovascular diseases. Parents play a very significant role in the physical activity of children. The action and behavior of Parents in relation to physical activity has an influence on the later life of children. Environmental and cultural factors also responsible in physical activity, safety measures for children and safe neighborhood environment is also very important in physical activity (Leung, 2014). The research is significant for parent's to improve their physical activity related awareness and for children to participate in such mental and physical development activities. The study is important for community to enhance their knowledge and change their behaviors related to physical activities of children.

Few amount of studies conducted in Pakistan on children physical activity, the aim of this study is to aware parents and children about physical activities.

Research Purpose

The main purpose of this study is to evaluate the parent's perception about their children physical activity.

Literature Review

Physical activity improves children's cognitive function, restores brain health, increase work memory and cognitive agility (Gao, Chen, Sun, Wen, & Xiang, 2018). World health organization recommends that children take part in routine moderate to intense physical activity for 60 minutes. Approximately 85 to 90% of children do not follow the recommended criteria for physical activity. Researcher found the link between parents and the physical activity level of their children. Parents have less parental involvement in children physical activity. According to theory of self-determination, adopting a supportive parenting style would foster competency, independence, communication that transform positive behavioral change and children psychological well-being (Ha, Ng, Lonsdale, Lubans, & Ng, 2019).

Researches showed that the requirements for weekly physical activity were met by only 62.7% of male children. The female children rate is also down from 51.7 % (England, 2014).

Pakistan has one of the world's lowest incidence rates (22%) of physically active children. This is because the community physical activity and play facilities have to keep pace with the country's rapid development. Other factors such as time spent on social media, veiwing television, playing video games and watching movies, interrupt the physical activity of children, which leads to increased weight (Ahmed et al., 2016).

One study shows that the motor skills of children increases with age. As the age of children's increase their motor activity also increases, children better understand the effects and also aid with their physical activity (Washburn & Kolen, 2018).

One study findings show about the parents perception of children's physical activity that between kindergarten and eighth grade children, about 13% of parents have more positive views,

8% have more negative views, and 16% have been mixed. The other parents who left constantly responded in all factors “slightly or not at all safe” (9%) or “really safe” (53%) (Datar, 2013).

Worldwide, the WHO has shown that female children are less involved in physical activities than male children, with prevalence disparities of 10% between them (WHO, 2016). The peak values of obesity among children aged 11 years, according to the World Health Organization (Bento, 2017).

Studies show parents awareness and value the physical activity in children. Parents perceive that school is the main source and provider of physical activity in children, schools motivate the children for physical activity (Trigwell, 2015).

Studies revealed that peri-urban mothers lack knowledge and misleading activities linked to children’s dietary habits and physical activity (Oli, 2015).

A smaller number of (24%) children between the ages of 6 to 17 years respond to body movement every day in 60 minutes. In 2017, only 26.1% of high school students contribute to physical activity in at least 60 minutes per day (Schools, 2016).

Researchers reported that physical inactivity causes at least 6% of the load associated with coronary heart disease, 7% of type 2 diabetes, 10% of breast cancer, and 10% of colon cancer. Physical inactivity, based on these figures is described as one of the 21 century’s major public health complications (Aubert, 2019).

Outdoor play is one of the main source of physical activity in children. The outdoor play study finds that the associated factors rely on children’s physical activity outside the house were: ethnicity of the mother, employment status of the mother, education level of the parents and the parent’s perception in the neighborhood social cohesion. Very few parents encouraged their children to play outside, especially for girls because of the neighborhood safety issues (Boxberger, Reimers, & health, 2019).

Physical education goal is to promote children health throughout their lifespan. One of the study results provide an evidence of the link in theoretical and practical elements of physical education that can improve the health of students (Haible et al., 2019).

Researches reviewed that physical competence revealed that the movement competence movement competence was based on gender and the evidence provided that the relationship

between physical competences, physical activity frequency and habitual physical activity flourished (Pill, Harvey, Studies, & Research, 2019).

Physical activity in children has declined over the past 20-30 years, leading to obesity and other cardiovascular diseases. Early childhood physical education and exercise should help academic and physical skills and behaviors (Ali, Pigou, Clarke, & McLachlan, 2017).

Methodology

Study Design: Cross sectional study, survey type research model and quantitative data which is obtained through a reliable and valid scales are used in the study.

Settings: The study will be conducted in Ali Raza Abad Community in Lahore, Pakistan.

Duration of Study: This study will be take approximately 3-4 months, from September 2019 to December 2019.

Target population: The population for this study is the parents of primary school children in community of Ali Raza Abad.

Sampling Technique: 195 parents were randomly choose for this study.

Equipment: In this study, the questionnaire is adopted from Carman Ka-man Leung (2014). The demographic data consist of 8 questions and the other section which is likert Scale questionnaire is consist of 70 questions.

Data Analysis

Data analyzed on SPSS version 21.0 frequencies, percentage, mean, median, mode and standard deviation applied on individual item. Data is collected through questionnaire. Distributed in 195 participants.

Results:-

Part-I Demographic Data

1. Age of the Parents:-

Table and figure no 1 shows that 36.9% (n=72) parents age is 20-30 years, 40% (n=78) parents age is 30-40 years, 18.5% (n=36) parents age is 40-50 years, 4.6% (n= 9) parents age is 50 and above.

Age	f	%
20-30 Years	72	36.9
30-40 Years	78	40.0
40-50 Years	36	18.5
50 and above	9	4.6
Total	195	100.0

Table No.1

Figure No. 1

2. Gender of the parents:-

Table and figure no 2 shows that 31.8% (n=62) are male parents and 68.2% (n=133) are female parents.

Gender	f	%
Male	62	31.8
Female	133	68.2
Total	195	100.0

Table No. 2

Figure No. 2

3. Education of parents:-

Table and figure no 3 shows that 25.6% (n=50) were no schooling, 40.5% (n=79) were primary school, 31.8% (n=62) were secondary school, 2.1% (n=4) were tertiary school and above.

Education	f	%
No schooling	50	25.6
Primary school	79	40.5
Secondary school	62	31.8
Tertiary school and above	4	2.1
Total	195	100.0

Table No. 3

Figure No. 3

4. Work status of parents:-

Table and figure no 4 shows that 22.1% (n=43) parents work in government job, 29.7% (n=58) parents work in private job, 46.2% (n=90) mothers are housewife, 2.1% (n=4) parents are searching for job.

Work status	f	%
Government job	43	22.1
Private job	58	29.7
Housewife	90	46.2
Searching for job	4	2.1
Total	195	100.0

Table No. 4

Figure No. 4

5. Income of parents:-

Table and figure no 5 shows that 25.6% (n=50) parents income is 1000-10000, 35.9% (n=70) parents income is 10000-20000, 20.0% (n=39) parents income is 20000-30000, 11.3% (n=22) parents income is 30000-40000, 7.2% (n=14) parents income is 40000 and above.

Income	f	%
1000-10000	50	25.6
10000-20000	70	35.9
20000-30000	39	20.0
30000-40000	22	11.3
40000 and above	14	7.2
Total	195	100.0

Table No. 5

Figure No. 5

6. Only parent

Table and figure no 6 shows that 11.8% (n=23) parents life partner is dead, 88.2% (n=172) parents life partner is alive.

Only parent	f	%
Yes	23	11.8
No	172	88.2
Total	195	100.0

Table No. 6

Figure No. 6

7. Child gender

Table and figure no 7 shows that 49.7% (n=97) children are boys, 50.3% (n=98) children are girls.

Child gender	f	%
Boy	97	49.7
Girl	98	50.3
Total	195	100.0

Table No. 7

Figure No. 7

8. Child age

Table and figure no 8 shows that 42.1% (n=82) children age is 5-7, 36.4% (n=71) children age is 8-10, 21.5% (n=42) children age is 11-13.

Child age	f	%
5-7	82	42.1
8-10	71	36.4
11-13	42	21.5
Total	195	100.0

Table No. 8

Figure No. 8

Part II

9. Section No. 1: This section related to child's physical competence.

Sr. no	Statements	Very true		Sort true		Not very true		Not at all true		mean	median	mode	s.d
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%				
1	My child does not do well at all sports.	107	54.9	51	26.2	13	6.7	24	12.3	1.76	1.00	1	1.028
2	My child does well at all sports.	44	22.6	64	32.8	51	26.2	36	18.5	2.41	2.00	2	1.033
3	My child is poorer at sports.	60	30.8	66	33.8	40	20.5	29	14.9	2.19	2.00	2	1.037
4	My child is better at sports.	46	23.6	52	26.7	61	31.3	36	18.5	2.45	2.00	3	1.046
5	My child does unwell at new activity.	71	36.4	58	29.7	43	22.1	23	11.8	2.09	2.00	1	1.026

6	My child does well at new activity.	45	23.1	48	24.6	51	26.2	51	26.2	2.55	3.00	3	1.113
7	My child is not good enough at sports.	57	29.2	72	36.9	40	20.5	26	13.3	2.18	2.00	2	1.002
8	My child is good enough at sports.	50	25.6	44	22.6	69	35.4	32	16.4	2.43	3.00	3	1.045
9	My child is not first chosen for games.	47	24.1	74	37.9	49	25.1	25	12.8	2.27	2.00	2	.969
10	My child is first chosen for games.	52	26.7	47	24.1	59	30.3	37	19.0	2.42	2.00	3	1.078
11	My child watch rather than play.	48	24.6	65	33.3	46	23.6	36	18.5	2.36	2.00	2	1.048
12	My child plays rather than watch.	41	21.0	52	26.7	57	29.2	45	23.1	2.54	3.00	3	1.066
13	My child is not good at new sports.	58	29.7	48	24.6	57	29.2	32	16.4	2.32	2.00	1	1.071
14	My child is good at new sports.	58	29.7	50	25.6	41	21.0	46	23.6	2.38	2.00	1	1.145

Table No. 9

As the table no 9 shows that the parents give answers about their children physical competence, children does not do well at all sports parents give answer as very true are 54.9% (n=107), sort of true are 26.2% (n=51), not very true are 6.7% (n=13), not at all true are 12.3% (n=24). Children who does well at all sports parents give answer as very true 22.6% (n=44), sort of true 32.8% (n=64), not very true 26.2% (n=51), not at all true 18.5% (n=36). Children who poorer at sports parents give answers as very true are 30.8% (n=60), sort of true 33.8% (n=66), not very true

20.5% (n=40), not at all true 14.9% (n=29). Children who better at sports parents give answers as very true 23.6% (n=46), sort of true 26.7% (n=52), not very true 31.3% (n=61), not at all true 18.5% (n=36). Children who does unwell at new activity parents give answer as very true are 36.4% (n=71), sort of true 29.7% (n=58), not very true 22.1% (n=43), not at all true 11.8% (n=23). Children who does well at new activity parents give answers as very true are 23.1% (n=45), sort of true 24.6% (n=48), not very true 26.2% (n=51), not at all true 26.2% (n=51). Children who are not good enough at sports parents give answers as very true are 29.2% (n=57), sort of true 36.9% (n=72), not very true 20.5% (n=40), not at all true 13.3% (n=26). Children who are good enough at sports parents give answers as very true are 25.6% (n=50), sort of true 22.6% (n=44), not very true 35.4% (n=69), not at all true 16.4% (n=32). Children who are not first chosen for games parents give answers as very true are 24.1% (n=47), sort of true 37.9% (n=74), not very true 25.1% (n=49), not at all true 12.8% (n=25). Children who are first chosen for games parents give answers as very true are 26.7% (n=52), sort of true 24.1% (n=47), not very true 30.3% (n=59), not at all true 19.0% (n=37). Children who watch rather than play parents give answers as very true are 24.6% (n=48), sort of true 33.3% (n=65), not very true 23.6% (n=46), not at all true 18.5% (n=36). Children who play rather than watch parents give answers as very true are 21.0% (n=41), sort of true 26.7% (n=52), not very true 29.2% (n=57), not at all true 23.1% (n=45). Children who are not good at new sports parents give answers as very true are 29.7% (n=58), sort of true 24.6% (n=48), not very true 29.2% (n=57), not at all true 16.4% (n=32). Children who are good at new sports parents give answers as very true are 29.7% (n=58), sort of true 25.6% (n=50), not very true 21.0% (n=41), not at all true 23.6% (n=46). The mean score for children physical competence is 2.31 and the overall mean score is ± 1.0505 .

10. Section No 2: This section is related to parent’s support in children physical activity.

Statements	None		One day a week		Three days a week		Five days a week		Daily		mean	median	mode	s.d
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%				
1) Encourage your child to do physical activities or	47	24.1	86	44.1	32	16.4	4	2.1	26	13.3	2.36	2.00	2	1.250

play sport?														
2) Do physical activities or play sports with their child?	23	11.8	77	39.5	55	28.2	8	4.1	32	16.4	2.74	2.00	2	1.226
3) Provide transportation so your child can go to a place where he or she can do physical activities or sport?	65	33.3	85	43.6	23	11.8	3	1.5	19	9.7	2.11	2.00	2	1.177
4) Watch your child participate in physical activity and sport?	30	15.4	77	39.5	62	31.8	5	2.6	21	10.8	2.54	2.00	2	1.123
5) Tell your child that physical activity is good for his or her health?	35	17.9	71	36.4	50	25.6	14	7.2	25	12.8	2.61	2.00	2	1.232

Table No.10

As the table no 10 shows that parents who encourage their children to do physical activity, none are 24.1% (n=47), one day a week 44.1% (n=86), three days a week 16.4% (n=32), five days a week 2.1% (n=4), daily 13.3% (n=26). Parents who do physical activities or play with their children are none 11.8% (n=23), one day a week 39.5% (n=77), three days a week 28.2% (n=55), five days a week 4.1% (n=8), daily 16.4% (n=32). Parents who provide transport for their

children to go on places where they can do physical activities or sport are none 33.3% (n=65), one day a week 43.6% (n=85), three days a week 11.8% (n=23), five days a week 1.5% (n=3), daily 9.7% (n=19). Parents who watch their children to participate in physical activity and sports are none 15.4% (n=30), one day a week 39.5% (n=77), three days a week 31.8% (n=62), five days a week 2.6% (n=5), daily 10.8% (n=21). Parents who tell their children that physical activity is good for their health are none 17.9% (n=35), one day a week 36.4% (n=71), three days a week 25.6% (n=50), five days a week 7.2% (n=14), daily 12.8% (n=25). The mean score for parents support their children in physical activity is 0.88 and the overall mean score is ± 0.428 .

11. Section No. 3: This section include perception of parents about the neighborhood safety for their children.

Statements	Never		Rarely		Sometimes		Frequently		mean	median	mode	s.d
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%				
How often you find the following things occur in the neighborhood?												
1) Drug dealers or users hanging around	73	37.4	95	48.7	24	12.3	3	1.5	1.78	2.00	2	.716
2) Drunks hanging around	37	19.0	106	54.4	45	23.1	7	3.6	2.11	2.00	2	.744
3) Unemployed adult loitering	46	23.6	90	46.2	51	26.2	8	4.1	2.11	2.00	2	.808
4) Young adults loitering	39	20.0	85	43.6	55	28.2	16	8.2	2.25	2.00	2	.868
5) Gang activity	46	23.6	72	36.9	57	29.2	20	10.3	2.26	2.00	2	.935
6) Disorderly or misbehaving groups of young children	37	19.0	75	38.5	67	34.4	16	8.2	2.32	2.00	2	.874

7) Disorderly or misbehaving groups of teenagers	33	16.9	88	45.1	58	29.7	16	8.2	2.29	2.00	2	.844
8) Disorderly or misbehaving groups of adults	51	26.2	70	35.9	61	31.3	13	6.7	2.18	2.00	2	.901

Table No. 11

Table no 11 shows about the parent’s perception about the neighborhood safety for their children which include drug dealers and users hanging around the answers of parents are never is 37.4% (n=73), rarely 48.7% (n=95), sometimes 12.3% (n=24), frequently 1.5% (n=3). Drunks hanging around the parents answer are never is 19.0% (n=37), rarely 54.4% (n=106), sometimes 23.1% (n=45), frequently 3.6% (n=7). Unemployed adult loitering the parents answer are never is 23.6% (n=46), rarely 46.2% (n=90), sometimes 26.2% (n=51), frequently 4.1% (n=8). Young adult loitering the parents answer are never is 20.0% (n=39), rarely 43.6% (n=85), sometimes 28.2% (n=55), frequently 8.2% (n=16). Any gang activity in neighborhood the parents answer are never is 23.6% (n=46), rarely 36.9% (n=72), sometimes 29.2% (n=57), frequently 10.3% (n=20). Disorderly or misbehave groups of youngsters and the parents answer are never is 19.0% (n=37), rarely 38.5% (n=75), sometimes 34.4% (n=67), frequently 8.2% (n=16). Disorderly or misbehave groups of teenagers and the parents answer are never is 16.9% (n=33), rarely 45.1% (n=88), sometimes 29.7% (n=58), frequently 8.2% (n=16). Disorderly or misbehave groups of adults and the parents answer are never is 26.2% (n=51), rarely 35.9% (n=70), sometimes 31.3% (n=61), frequently 6.7% (n=13). The mean score for parents perception about neighborhood safety for children is 2.16 and the overall mean score is ±0.84.

12. Section No. 4: This section include parent’s ideas about their children exercise.

Statements	Strongly agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly disagree		mean	median	mode	s.d
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%				

1) My child enjoys exercise.	80	41.0	104	53.3	10	5.1	1	.5	1.65	2.00	2	.602
2) Exercise decreases feelings of stress and tension for my child.	48	24.6	100	59.5	31	15.9	16	13.2	1.91	2.00	2	.632
3) Exercise improves my child's mental health.	36	18.5	121	62.1	34	17.4	4	2.1	2.03	2.00	2	.665
4) Exercising takes too much of my child's time.	41	21.0	113	57.9	36	18.5	5	2.6	2.03	2.00	2	.707
5) My child will prevent heart attacks by exercising.	37	19.0	114	58.5	38	19.5	6	3.1	2.07	2.00	2	.711
6) Exercise tires my child.	44	22.6	94	48.2	50	25.6	7	3.6	2.10	2.00	2	.786
7) Exercise increases my child's muscle strength.	48	24.6	95	48.7	42	21.5	10	5.1	2.07	2.00	2	.815
8) Exercise gives my child a sense of personal accomplishment.	44	22.6	102	52.3	44	22.6	5	2.6	2.05	2.00	2	.744
9) Places for my child to exercise are too far away.	41	21.0	101	51.8	41	21.0	12	6.2	2.12	2.00	2	.809

10) Exercising makes my child feel relaxes.	41	21.0	91	46.7	55	28.2	8	4.1	2.15	2.00	2	.797
11) Exercising lets my child have contact with friends and persons I enjoy.	40	20.5	85	43.6	55	28.2	15	7.7	2.23	2.00	2	.863
12) My child is too embarrassed to exercise.	39	20.0	93	47.7	47	24.1	16	8.2	2.21	2.00	2	.855
13) Exercising will keep my child from having high blood pressure.	49	25.1	85	43.6	46	23.6	15	7.7	2.14	2.00	2	.883
14) It costs too much money to exercise.	97	49.7	84	43.1	12	6.2	2	1.0	1.58	2.00	1	.655
15) Exercising increases my child's level of physical fitness.	49	25.1	117	60.0	24	12.3	5	2.6	1.92	2.00	2	.688
16) Exercise facilities do not have convenient schedules for my child.	49	25.1	103	52.8	42	21.5	1	.5	1.97	2.00	2	.699
17) My muscle tone is improved with exercise.	47	24.1	112	57.4	28	14.4	8	4.1	1.98	2.00	2	.743
18) Exercising	51	26.2	98	50.3	36	18.5	10	5.1	2.03	2.00	2	.809

improves functioning of my child's cardiovascular system.												
19) My child is fatigued by exercise.	68	34.9	88	45.1	30	15.4	9	4.6	1.90	2.00	2	.825
20) My child has improved feelings of well-being from exercise.	60	30.8	85	43.6	40	20.5	10	5.1	2.00	2.00	2	.849
21) My spouse (or significant other) does not encourage exercising.	53	27.2	91	46.7	38	19.5	13	6.7	2.06	2.00	2	.857
22) Exercise increases my child's stamina.	61	31.3	83	42.6	36	18.5	15	7.7	2.03	2.00	2	.899
23) Exercise improves my child's flexibility.	47	24.1	92	47.2	34	17.4	22	11.3	2.16	2.00	2	.920
24) Exercise takes too much time from family relationships.	55	28.2	93	47.7	36	18.5	11	5.6	2.02	2.00	2	.834
25) My disposition is improved by exercise.	53	27.2	93	47.7	47	24.1	2	1.0	1.99	2.00	2	.746
26) Exercising helps	60	30.8	85	43.6	44	22.6	6	3.1	1.98	2.00	2	.812

my child sleep better at night.												
27) My child will live longer if he or she exercises.	64	32.8	83	42.6	39	20.0	9	4.6	1.96	2.00	2	.846
28) My child thinks people in exercise clothes look funny.	43	22.1	101	51.8	45	23.1	6	3.1	2.07	2.00	2	.756
29) Exercise helps my child decrease fatigue.	54	27.7	87	44.6	48	24.6	6	3.1	2.03	2.00	2	.805
30) Exercising is a good way for my child to meet new people.	47	24.1	92	47.2	48	24.6	8	4.1	2.09	2.00	2	.804
31) My physical endurance is improved by exercising.	48	24.6	87	44.6	58	29.7	2	1.0	2.07	2.00	2	.763
32) Exercising improves my child's self-concept.	53	27.2	88	45.1	45	23.1	9	4.6	2.05	2.00	2	.830
33) My family members including me do not encourage my child to exercise.	62	31.8	73	37.4	50	25.6	10	5.1	2.04	2.00	2	.884
34) Exercising increases my	47	24.1	91	46.7	47	24.1	10	5.1	2.10	2.00	2	.825

child's mental alertness.												
35) Exercise allows my child to carry out normal activities without becoming tired.	47	24.1	81	41.5	57	29.2	10	5.1	2.15	2.00	2	.848
36) Exercise improves the quality of my child's work.	50	25.6	85	43.6	44	22.6	16	8.2	2.13	2.00	2	.893
37) Exercise to my child takes too much time from family responsibilities.	53	27.2	85	43.6	45	23.1	12	6.2	2.08	2.00	2	.864
38) Exercise is good entertainment for my child.	59	30.3	74	37.9	48	24.6	14	7.2	2.09	2.00	2	.912
39) Exercising increases my child's acceptance by others.	47	24.1	92	47.2	46	23.6	10	5.1	2.10	2.00	2	.822
40) Exercise is hard work for my child.	39	20.0	95	48.7	51	26.2	10	5.1	2.16	2.00	2	.802
41) Exercise improves overall body functioning for my child.	41	21.0	101	51.8	43	22.1	10	5.1	2.11	2.00	2	.791

42) There are too few places for my child to exercise.	47	24.1	84	43.1	48	24.6	16	8.2	2.17	2.00	2	.889
43) Exercise improves the way my child's body looks.	45	23.1	94	48.2	41	21.0	15	7.7	2.13	2.00	2	.857

Table No. 12

Table no 12 shows about the parent's idea about their children exercise included children enjoys exercise strongly agree are 41.0% (n=80), agree 53.3% (n=104), disagree 5.1% (n=10), strongly disagree .5% (n=1). Exercise decreases feelings of stress and tension of children strongly agree are 24.6% (n=48), agree 59.5% (n=100), disagree 15.9% (n=31), strongly disagree 13.2% (n=16). Exercise improves children mental health strongly agree are 18.5% (n=36), agree 62.1% (n=121), disagree 17.4% (n=34), strongly disagree 2.1% (n=4). Exercising takes too much of children time strongly agree are 21.0% (n=41), agree 57.9% (n=113), disagree 18.5% (n=36), strongly disagree 2.6% (n=5). Children will prevent heart attack by exercising strongly agree are 19.0% (n=37), agree 58.5% (n=114), disagree 19.5% (n=38), strongly disagree 3.1% (n=6). Exercise tires children strongly agree are 22.6% (n=44), agree 48.2% (n=94), disagree 25.6% (n=50), strongly disagree 3.6% (n=7). Exercise increases children muscle strength strongly agree are 24.6% (n=48), agree 48.7% (n=95), disagree 21.5% (n=42), strongly disagree 5.1% (n=10). Exercise gives children a sense of personal accomplishment strongly agree are 22.6% (n=44), agree 52.3% (n=102), disagree 22.6% (n=44), strongly disagree 2.6% (n=5). Places for the children to exercise are too far away strongly agree are 21.0% (n=41), agree 51.8% (n=101), disagree 21.0% (n=41), strongly disagree 6.2% (n=12). Exercise makes children feel relax strongly agree are 21.0% (n=41), agree 46.7% (n=91), disagree 28.2% (n=55), strongly disagree 4.1% (n=8). Exercising lets children contact with friends strongly agree are 20.5% (n=40), agree 43.6% (n=85), disagree 28.2% (n=55), strongly disagree 7.7% (n=15). Children embarrassed to exercise strongly agree are 20.0% (n=39), agree 47.7% (n=93), disagree 24.1% (n=47), strongly disagree 8.2% (n=16). Exercising will keep children from having high blood pressure strongly agree are 25.1% (n=49), agree 43.6% (n=85), disagree 23.6% (n=46), strongly disagree 7.7% (n=15). It cost too much money to exercise strongly agree are 49.7% (n=97), agree 43.1%

(n=84), disagree 6.2% (n=12), strongly disagree 1.0% (n=2). Exercise increases children physical fitness strongly agree are 25.1% (n=49), agree 60.0% (n=117), disagree 12.3% (n=24), strongly disagree 2.6% (n=5). Exercise facilities do not have convenient schedules for children strongly agree are 25.1% (n=49), agree 52.8% (n=103), disagree 21.5% (n=42), strongly disagree .5% (n=1). Children muscle tone is improved with exercise strongly agree are 24.1% (n=47), agree 57.4% (n=112), disagree 14.4% (n=28), strongly disagree 4.1% (n=8). Exercising improves functioning of children cardiovascular system strongly agree are 26.2% (n=51), agree 50.3% (n=98), disagree 18.5% (n=36), strongly disagree 5.1% (n=10). Children are fatigued by exercise strongly agree are 34.9% (n=68), agree 45.1% (n=88), disagree 15.4% (n=30), strongly disagree 4.6% (n=9). Children has improved feelings of wellbeing from exercise strongly agree are 30.8% (n=60), agree 43.6% (n=85), disagree 20.5% (n=40), strongly disagree 5.1% (n=10). Spouse does not encourage exercising strongly agree are 27.2% (n=53), agree 46.7% (n=91), disagree 19.5% (n=38), strongly disagree 6.7% (n=13). Exercise increases children stamina strongly agree are 31.3% (n=61), agree 42.6% (n=83), disagree 18.5% (n=36), strongly disagree 7.7% (n=15). Exercise improves children flexibility strongly agree are 24.1% (n=47), agree 47.2% (n=92), disagree 17.4% (n=34), strongly disagree 11.3% (n=22). Exercise takes too much time from family relationships strongly agree are 28.2% (n=55), agree 47.7% (n=93), disagree 18.5% (n=36), strongly disagree 5.6% (n=11). Disposition is improved by exercise strongly agree are 27.2% (n=53), agree 47.7% (n=93), disagree 24.1% (n=47), strongly disagree 1.0% (n=2). Exercise helps children sleep better at night strongly agree are 30.8% (n=60), agree 43.6% (n=85), disagree 22.6% (n=44), strongly disagree 3.1% (n=6). Children live longer if they exercise strongly agree are 32.8% (n=64), agree 42.6% (n=83), disagree 20.0% (n=39), strongly disagree 4.6% (n=9). Children thinks people in exercise clothes look funny strongly agree are 22.1% (n=43), agree 51.8% (n=101), disagree 23.1% (n=45), strongly disagree 3.1% (n=6). Exercise helps children to decrease fatigue strongly agree are 27.7% (n=54), agree 44.6% (n=87), disagree 24.6% (n=48), strongly disagree 3.1% (n=6). Exercising is a good way for children to meet new people strongly agree are 24.1% (n=47), agree 47.2% (n=92), disagree 24.6% (n=48), strongly disagree 4.1% (n=8). Physical endurance is improved by exercising strongly agree are 24.6% (n=48), agree 44.6% (n=87), disagree 29.7% (n=58), strongly disagree 1.0% (n=2). Exercising improves children self-concept strongly agree are 27.2% (n=53), agree 45.1% (n=88), disagree 23.1% (n=45), strongly disagree 4.6% (n=9). Family members do not

encourage children to exercise strongly agree are 31.8% (n=62), agree 37.4% (n=73), disagree 25.6% (n=50), strongly disagree 5.1% (n=10). Exercising increases children mental alertness strongly agree are 24.1% (n=47), agree 46.7% (n=91), disagree 24.1% (n=47), strongly disagree 5.1% (n=10). Exercise allows children to carry out normal activities without becoming tired strongly agree are 24.1% (n=47), agree 41.5% (n=81), disagree 29.2% (n=57), strongly disagree 5.1% (n=10). Exercise improves the quality of children work strongly agree are 25.6% (n=50), agree 43.6% (n=85), disagree 22.6% (n=44), strongly disagree 8.2% (n=16). Exercise of children takes too much time from family responsibilities strongly agree are 27.2% (n=53), agree 43.6% (n=85), disagree 23.1% (n=45), strongly disagree 6.2% (n=12). Exercise is good entertainment for children strongly agree are 30.3% (n=59), agree 37.9% (n=74), disagree 24.6% (n=48), strongly disagree 7.2% (n=14). Exercising increases children acceptance by others strongly agree are 24.1% (n=47), agree 47.2% (n=92), disagree 23.6% (n=46), strongly disagree 5.1% (n=10). Exercise is hard work for children strongly agree are 20.0% (n=39), agree 48.7% (n=95), disagree 26.2% (n=51), strongly disagree 5.1% (n=10). Exercise improves overall body functioning for children strongly agree are 21.0% (n=41), agree 51.8% (n=101), disagree 22.1% (n=43), strongly disagree 5.1% (n=10). There are too few places for children to exercise strongly agree are 24.1% (n=47), agree 43.1% (n=84), disagree 24.6% (n=48), strongly disagree 8.2% (n=16). Exercise improves the way children body look strongly agree are 23.1% (n=45), agree 48.2% (n=94), disagree 21.0% (n=41), strongly disagree 7.7% (n=15). The mean score for the parents ideas about exercise is 1.99 and the overall mean score is ± 0.799 .

Discussion

This study is based on the parent's perception of children physical activity, data was collected from Ali Raza Abad community parents of primary school children. Likert scale questionnaire is used to conduct data. The sample size for this study is 195 parents, total male parents were 31.8% and female parents were 61.2% participate to fill the survey questionnaire. 40.5% of parents are going to primary school and only 2.1% of parents went to tertiary school it means the illiteracy rate is higher among parents. The only parent's rate is 11.8% and the other parent's life partners are alive 88.2% it means both parents participate in children development. The main focus of this study is to analyze firstly the parent's perception about the children physical competence the results shows that children who have very minimum physical competence are 54.9% and the children who have maximum physical competence are 11.8%. Secondly parents who support their children in physical activity one day a week maximum is 44.1% and five days a week minimum is 1.5%. Thirdly parent's perception about neighborhood safety of their children maximum parents are worried about safety measure which is 48.7%, and minimum 1.5% of parents are not excessively worried about the children safety in neighborhood. Fourthly parent's ideas about exercise for their children 57.4% of parents believe that exercise is beneficial for their children and 1.0% of parents are strongly disagree on it. This study determines that parent's knowledge, education and participation is very important for children physical growth.

The other studies suggested that parent's perception and knowledge is very important for children physical activity. Parents should aware about its benefits and its consequences. Environment and school is the main provider of children physical activity, for girls there is a cultural related physical activities (Trigwell, 2015).

Some studies shows that, Lower street connectivity and higher neighborhood aesthetics correlated with higher reported child activity in the neighborhood, while reported safety from crime and walk and cycle facilities correlated positively with reported child activity in public recreation spaces (Tappe, 2013).

Strength of the Study

There are several strength in this study for example parenting status dual parents are more capable of providing an environment best for the children for physical activities and single parent is mostly afraid because of neighborhood and other safety measures. Secondly there were no study conducted in Pakistan related to parent's perception about children physical activity. The study in Pakistan, Hyderabad conducted on the topic of parental and school influences on physical activity level of high school students (Ahmed et al., 2016).

Limitation

The limitation for this study was to focus on the parents and children. Time duration for this study is too short. The study involved cross sectional design. Closed ended questions related to the topic are used.

Conclusion

This study examined parent's perceptions about children's competence of physical activity, neighborhood safety, exercise benefits and exercise barriers, parental support, and parents views about the children's physical activity. Each of the relationships among the above constructs was analyzed. Parent's involvement is very significant for children physical activity. The parents who have minimum knowledge about physical activity had a weaker children throughout life span. Some parents afraid from neighborhood environment and don't support their children especially girls for physical activity. There are also some socio-cultural factor that effect physical activity of children.

References:-

- Ahmed, J., et al. (2016). "Parental and school influences on physical activity levels of high school students in Hyderabad, Pakistan." 28(1): 110-115.
- Aubert, S., Barnes, J. D., Forse, M. L., Turner, E., González, S. A., Kalinowski, J., & Schranz, N. (2019). The International Impact of the Active Healthy Kids Global Alliance Physical Activity Report Cards for Children and Youth. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 1(aop), 1-19.
- Ali, A., Pigou, D., Clarke, L., & McLachlan, C. (2017). Literature review on motor skill and physical activity in preschool children in New Zealand.
- Bento, G., & Dias, G. (2017). The importance of outdoor play for young children's healthy development. *Porto Biomedical Journal*, 2(5), 157-160.
- Beck, A. M., Eyster, A. A., Hipp, J. A., King, A. C., Tabak, R. G., Yan, Y., ... & Brownson, R. C. (2019). A multilevel approach for promoting physical activity in rural communities: a cluster randomized controlled trial. *BMC public health*, 19(1), 126.
- Boxberger, K., & Reimers, A. K. (2019). Parental Correlates of Outdoor Play in Boys and Girls Aged 0 to 12—A Systematic Review. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(2), 190.
- Datar, A., Nicosia, N., & Shier, V. (2013). Parent perceptions of neighborhood safety and children's physical activity, sedentary behavior, and obesity: evidence from a national longitudinal study. *American journal of epidemiology*, 177(10), 1065-1073.
- England, P. H. (2014). Everybody active, every day: a framework to embed physical activity into daily life.
- Guthold, R., Stevens, G. A., Riley, L. M., & Bull, F. C. (2018). Worldwide trends in insufficient physical activity from 2001 to 2016: a pooled analysis of 358 population-based surveys with 1·9 million participants. *The Lancet Global Health*, 6(10), e1077-e1086.
- Gao, Z., et al. (2018). "Physical Activity in Children's Health and Cognition." 2018.

- Haible, S., Volk, C., Demetriou, Y., Höner, O., Thiel, A., Trautwein, U., & Sudeck, G. (2019). Promotion of physical activity-related health competence in physical education: study protocol for the GEKOS cluster randomized controlled trial. *BMC public health*, *19*(1), 396.
- Ha, A. S., et al. (2019). "Promoting physical activity in children through family-based intervention: protocol of the "Active 1+ FUN" randomized controlled trial." *19*(1): 218.
- Jago, R., et al. (2017). "Association of parents' and children's physical activity and sedentary time in Year 4 (8–9) and change between Year 1 (5–6) and Year 4: a longitudinal study." *14*(1): 110.
- Jabeen, I., Zuberi, R., & Nanji, K. (2018). Physical activity levels and their correlates among secondary school adolescents in a township of Karachi, Pakistan. *cardiovascular diseases*, *2*, 4.
- Kamal, S. A., & Khan, S. A. (2014). Primary-physical-education practices in Pakistan and England: Health and safety perspectives. *International Journal of Biology and Biotechnology*, *11*(2&3), 401-419.
- Lago-Ballesteros, J., Martins, J., González-Valeiro, M. Á., & Fernández-Villarino, M. A. (2019). Parental assessment of physical education in the school curriculum: A brief report on the influence of past experiences as students. *PloS one*, *14*(7), e0219544.
- Leung, C. K.-m. (2014). "Parents' perceptions of children's physical activities."
- Lewis, B. (2012). *Papa's Baby: Paternity and Artificial Insemination*. NYU Press.
- McKinney, J., Lithwick, D. J., Morrison, B. N., Nazzari, H., Isserow, S. H., Heilbron, B., & Krahn, A. D. (2016). The health benefits of physical activity and cardiorespiratory fitness. *British Columbia Medical Journal*, *58*(3), 131-137.
- Mikaelsson, K., Rutberg, S., Lindqvist, A. K., & Michaelson, P. (2019). Physically inactive adolescents' experiences of engaging in physical activity. *European Journal of Physiotherapy*, 1-6
- Nordqvist, C. (2014). Health: What does good health really mean?. *Medical News Today*.

Onebunne, J. I., & Odoh, E. (2018). CRITICALLY QUESTIONING THE NIGERIAN VERSION OF CHILD'S RIGHT BROUHAHA. *Journal Of Moral Education In Africa*, 3.

Oli, N., Vaidya, A., Subedi, M., Eiben, G., & Krettek, A. (2015). Diet and physical activity for children's health: a qualitative study of Nepalese mothers' perceptions. *BMJ open*, 5(9), e008197.

Piercy, K. L., Troiano, R. P., Ballard, R. M., Carlson, S. A., Fulton, J. E., Galuska, D. A., ... & Olson, R. D. (2018). The physical activity guidelines for Americans. *Jama*, 320(19), 2020- 2028.

Pill, S., & Harvey, S. (2019). A Narrative Review of Children's Movement Competence Research 1997-2017. *Physical Culture and Sport. Studies and Research*, 81(1), 47-74.

Rizwan, B., Khan, M. A., Farooq, S., Khalid, S., & Ahmad, B. Prevalence of Physical Inactivity Among The Students of University Institute of Diet and Nutritional Sciences, University of Lahore.

Schools, H. (2016). *Physical Activity Facts*. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Retrieved 9/19/2017 from <https://www.cdc.gov/healthyschools/physicalactivity/facts.htm>.

Schoeppe, S., et al. (2016). "The influence of parental modelling on children's physical activity and screen time: Does it differ by gender?" *27*(1): 152-157.

Trigwell, J., Murphy, R. C., Cable, N. T., Stratton, G., & Watson, P. M. (2015). Parental views of children's physical activity: a qualitative study with parents from multi-ethnic backgrounds living in England. *BMC Public Health*, 15(1), 1005.

Tremblay, M. S., Gray, C. E., Akinroye, K., Harrington, D. M., Katzmarzyk, P. T., Lambert, E. V. & Prista, A. (2014). Physical activity of children: a global matrix of grades comparing 15 countries. *Journal of physical activity and health*, 11(s1), S113-S125.

Tappe, K. A., Glanz, K., Sallis, J. F., Zhou, C., & Saelens, B. E. (2013). Children's physical activity and parents' perception of the neighborhood environment: neighborhood impact on kids study. *International journal of behavioral nutrition and physical activity*, 10(1), 39.

World Health Organization. (2016). Global Health Observatory (GHO) data: prevalence of insufficient physical activity. *Geneva: WHO. Available on http://www.who.int/gho/ncd/risk_factors/physical_activity_text/en.*

Washburn, R. and A. J. C. Kolen (2018). "Children's Self-Perceived and Actual Motor Competence in Relation to Their Peers." **5**(6): 72.

© GSJ